

ISSUES OF TECHNICAL EQUIPMENT OF SCHOOL CLASSROOMS ON THE BASIS OF INNOVATIONS

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Abstract

In this article the concept of “innovation” from the point of view of technological approach is considered. Within the framework of this article a complex author's research of the problem of technical equipment of classrooms in domestic schools is carried out, a qualitatively new strategy of equipping school classrooms with technical equipment that meets the requirements of the new generation is developed.

Keywords: innovation, VR-reality, holograms, interactive tables, efficiency.

Introduction

The problem of innovative technical support of the education process in Uzbekistan plays a significant role and affects the quality of the level of knowledge of young people and the results in the field of scientific achievements. Introduction of new forms, methods, including technical ones, and skills in the sphere of training, education and science are a kind of locomotive of progress in the educational process. Some technical developments that have not received the status of mass application, but interesting and demanded in the learning process can be considered innovative. The need for wide application of such innovations as: VR reality, holograms, 3D modeling is already relevant in the educational process today.

Method

The problem of actualization of technical equipment in domestic schools has recently attracted more and more attention of the scientific community. The level of technical innovation support of the educational process directly affects the results of perception and assimilation of material by schoolchildren. The need for modernization of educational equipment almost everywhere requires new economic investments on the one hand, and on the other hand needs to attract highly qualified specialists who provide this type of activity. That is, teachers must have the appropriate level of training for the effective use of

innovative technologies in the learning process. Such technologies include: VR-technologies, holograms and interactive tables.

Discussion

VR-technologies create a virtual space that immerses students in the world of a topic, helping them to focus on its study. When studying a chemical equation in a VR-equipped classroom, students get inside a chemical reaction by watching particles combine. Google Expeditions, zSpace, ClassVR, Immersive VR Education, Labster, VR for Special Education - this is a small list of VR solutions in education.

The use of virtual reality technologies in teaching allows:

- give schoolchildren direct, rather than theoretical, experience;
- reduce the impact of distractions that interfere with the perception of information;
- explain difficult to understand phenomena and subjects.

Scientists around the world support the use of VR-technologies for learning as facilitating understanding and memorization of material. Any skills are easier to master if practiced in an interactive, three-dimensional environment. It should be noted that VR-technology is not only screens and glasses designed for students to perceive information, it is also a multifunctional panel for the teacher. The teacher receives a signal from the students' displays, launching materials and monitoring their learning progress. He can also become a part of three-dimensional virtual reality to explain the processes taking place or to draw students' attention to any details.

The modern world is impossible to imagine without technology, just a few years ago 3D technology was a “know-how”, but even today it can be said yesterday. Today the innovation in this direction is holograms. Hologram is a technology of projection of three-dimensional volumetric image, which turns the image into reality. Nowadays, holograms are actively used in such fields as medicine, astronomy, engineering.

Holograms have gained their popularity quite recently. The advantages of holograms are as follows:

- the hologram can be walked around and viewed from all sides;
- the hologram has depth;
- it is formed in space, and a 3D picture
- is just an illusion of volume;

— to create and demonstrate holograms one can use an ordinary smartphone, which every pupil possesses.

The application of holograms in the educational process will improve it. Unique possibilities of using and application of three-dimensional holograms in training will allow not only to show the object in 360 degrees, but also allows and encourages students to actively interact with it: twist, zoom in, zoom out. This makes the learning process interactive, visual, visual, exciting, creative, which allows to continue to form the necessary competencies in students. So a gadget that interferes with the educational process becomes one of the means of learning. And its use within the educational process to demonstrate the developed materials on 3D holograms allows learning to individualize.

Holograms, when used in education, have a number of characteristics that become advantages over other types of visualization:

- Provide interactions with the object on an intuitive level;
- Provide information here and now (no special skills and knowledge are required for viewing);
- Show things that cannot be visualized in conventional ways;
- Provide the ability to easily change the parameters of an object;
- Provide an opportunity to “try on” holographic objects to the real environment;
- Any teacher can create holograms and does not need necessary skills and specialized software.

Another innovation in education is an interactive table for children - equipment based on microprocessor technology for learning in the process of collective interaction with a computer. A team of up to 10 students can work at the display simultaneously. Interactive equipment is used at different stages of the lesson: at the time of presentation of new material, laboratory, practical work and experiments, as well as at the stage of consolidation of material and testing the level of knowledge. At the moment of interaction with the table, children learn to solve educational tasks together with the teacher and develop their communication skills. The work promotes team building and helps students to become courteous and flexible. The interactive touch table can be used in the study of various subject disciplines within the school program or extracurricular activities. With the help of the gadget schoolchildren can perform mathematical operations, learn the basics of geometry, science, study letters and foreign languages.

Tables have tons of features:

- Software with visual tools and picture storage.
- Creating digital material, viewing digital maps and drawing board.
- Support for an electronic school journal.
- Working in separate areas of the screen on individual assignments.
- Independent simultaneous work in browsers.
- Customizable interface.
- Authorization of all users.

In order to optimize the learning process, interactive equipment is effectively used, which makes it possible to effectively train teaching staff and interest schoolchildren in standard disciplines. Educational institutions can save money on the purchase of books, printed materials, visual aids, laboratory equipment.

Interactive table for school is characterized by the following benefits:

- Effective assimilation of the educational program due to the impact of sound, graphics, text;
- Development of collective interaction in groups;
- Taking into account the abilities and achievements of each student;
- Control over the course of the lesson, taking into account the time and speed of presentation of the material;
- Reducing the load on the teacher.

To choose an excellent interactive developmental table for use in the educational institution, it is important to consider not only the cost of the model. It is necessary to assess the type of operating system, the possibility of quick service and repair of the firm center, equipment software and instructions.

Conclusion

In case of realization of such opportunities, the quality of the educational process in Uzbekistan will be improved, which means that in the future we can hope for higher results in the field of science and education.

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